

LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

Mokhichekhra Khakimova

English teacher at school N32 in Namangan district

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13923529>

Abstract

English is an international language which is used officially all around the world. English can connect society with the world in various aspects. Anybody who wants to make connections with the world should learn English. We as a society with English is not the main language in our country, it is necessary to learn English in order to reach the outside world. Learn English can be from anywhere, learn English from college, internet, English tutoring, and social media too. To make English as a second language in our life, we need to understand the basic of English and appropriate learning strategy.

Key-Words : International language, Learn English, Second language

Introduction

In this global era, English has successfully placed its position as a language in multicultural and communication, as a language in international business communication, and as a language in the international language of research (Rintaningrum, 2016). As the most popular used language in the world, in various forms, English is estimated spoken by 400 million people as a mother tongue and an additional 2 billion as a second and/or foreign language (Demont-Heinrich, 2007). By mastering English, we can improve ourselves both in academic and life skills that the outside world needs right now. However this is also not an excuse to shut yourself off from the development of the outside world, including not wanting to learn English. Then, what is the meaning of learning English as a second language? Why should we learn English as a second language? And the last what are the strategies for learning English as a second language? This will be explained later in the discussion.

Content/Discussion

1. The Meaning of Learning English as a Second Language (ESL)
English as a second language (ESL) is a traditional term for the use or study of the English language by non-native speakers in an English-speaking environment (it is also known as English for speakers of other language). English as a second language also refers to specialized approaches to language teaching designed for those whose primary language is not English (Nordquist, 2019). A simple way to define language learning is the process which the language capability develops in an individual. Learning language per say takes

strategies, and according to Wenden and Rubin, learning strategies can be defined as actions, steps, plans or routines taken by the learners in processing the information they received (Hashim, 2018). So, from the combination of these 2 understandings, Learning English as a Second Language is a learning method that refers to specialized approaches to language teaching designed for those whose primary language is not English, where in the learning process it can be through as actions, steps, plans or routines taken by the learners in processing the information they received.

2. Why should we learn English as a Second Language? We should learn English as a second language because at this time, English is an international language which is the language of communication to connect us with the development of the outside world. By mastering English, it gives us more opportunities to travel to various parts of the world without being hindered by communication. In addition, by learning English as a second language, it will give us more job opportunities so that we can follow developments in the outside world regarding future careers.

3. The factors that make citizens still not able to apply English as a Second Language. In this modern era, mastering English has become a necessity. We as Indonesians who are born with different mother tongue, there may be some obstacles in learning English as an effort to apply English as a second language in Indonesia. In cases, when spoken English in everyday life, the answers are still stammered, nervous, or may not relate to English conversations. So, here are some factors that make Indonesians citizens still not able to apply English as a Second Language :

✓ Environment factor

Unwittingly, environment factor cause English to be more difficult to apply as a second language. Sayings from the environment such as “Don’t act like a foreigner” or “Don’t speak English pretentious”, these words make learners who already wants to learn English becomes down and afraid to be ridiculed by their peers. This ridicule and innuendo made their self-confidence lower and they were reluctant to continue learning English. So, this one of the factors that makes English difficult as a second language

✓ Lack of motivation to learn English as a second language Using mother tongue is often used as an excuse to delay learning English. This happens because of a lack of motivation to learn English, so citizens of a particular country are lazy to learn English, even though English is very much needed to deal with the outside world which is growing rapidly.

- ✓ Too monotonous learning model

Currently, technology has developed rapidly, so we can access various kinds of information, including accessing information about learning English. However, most of us only learn English from books and don't apply English in everyday life (rarely speak in English), even though, there are many other learning media to learn English, such as internet, English tutoring on youtube, and social media too. So, this one of the factors that makes English difficult to apply in Indonesia.

- ✓ There are some English materials that are difficult for some people where the mother tongue is not English

English is difficult for some people where the mother tongue is not English because mostly due to its unpredictable spelling and tricky to master grammar. In addition, there are many words in the English language that supposedly mean the same thing, of course this can seem confusing or difficult for some people where the mother tongue is not English. Furthermore, beyond spelling and meaning lies pronunciation, which can also cause confusion those learning English. Therefore, appropriate and fun learning strategies are needed in learning English as a second language.

4. Strategies for Learning English as a Second Language
Before going further to strategies for learning English as a second language, here are the basics English that we must understand is :

a) Tenses, tenses or word forms are the most important and fundamental elements for learning English.

b) Listening, listening is one of the skills or abilities of the English language whose application is to listen to the vocabulary in English sentences. One of the ways quickly learn English is to get used listening to the words in English. However, it's not that easy to learn listening. Listening is not as easy as people think, particularly when the English language has status as a foreign language that is different from a second language as well as first language (Rintaningrum, 2018).

c) Reading, reading is by reading some text or sentences in English, it will make us more sensitive to the structure of words formed in the language English so as to get a lot of new vocabulary in English.

d) Writing, writing is one of the basics in learning English, writing will make understand about our ability to speak English, whether it's from grammar or vocabulary.

e) Speaking, speaking is the stage where students after mastering tenses, listening, reading, and writing, get used to speaking the English language, we will always get used to foreign words that may feel difficult spoken by the common people. Even if slowly, if we practice it often, it will make our speaking skills sound fluent like caucasians.

In order to achieve the goal of learning English as a second language, in my view, strategies are needed, namely:

1. Learn English through various media or sources Because at this time technology is increasingly modern, it allows us to learn something not only from books, but also other media such as social media, Youtube, online English learning applications, etc. By accessing some of these learning media, our knowledge of the material in English will be wider. Learning English with other people (native speakers), in addition to training our confidence, also helps improve the quality of learning English as a second language.

2. Practicing English in daily life As in the previous citation that the learning process it can be through as actions, steps, plans or routines taken by the learners in processing the information theyreceived. With that citation, we need to put what we have achieved in learning

English as a second language into everyday life. For example, learning to write using English and practicing English in communicating (training speaking and listening skills).

Conclusion

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that learning English as a second language is very necessary. This is because in this global era, English has successfully placed its position as a language in multicultural and communication, as a language in international business communication, and as a language in the international language of research. English is also estimated spoken by 400 million people as a mother tongue and an additional 2 billion as a second and/or foreign language. Learning English is needed to face the fast development of the outside world. Then how to learn English as a second language can be applied, by learning English through various sources or media and practicing it in everyday life, because the best way to master English is to practice listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills in English.

References:

1. Demont-Heinrich, C. (2008). American triumphalism and the "Offensive" defensiveness of the French: French as a Foil for English in U.S. Prestige Press Coverage of the global Hegemony of English. *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, 32(271), 271-291.

2. Hashim, H. U. (2018). English as a Second Language (ESL) Learning: Setting the Right Environment for Second Language Acquisition. E-Journal, 3.
3. <http://ejournal.radenintan.ac.id/index.php/tadris/article/view/2941/pdf>
4. Nordquist, Richard. "Definition of English as a Second Language (ESL)." ThoughtCo, Aug. 27, 2020, [thoughtco.com/english-as-a-second-language-esl-1690599](https://www.thoughtco.com/english-as-a-second-language-esl-1690599).
5. Rintaningrum, R. (2016). I Find It Easy To Learn English When.....: Lecturers' Perspective. Jambi University Press, 1-12

